

ISic3216

I.Sicily inscription 3216

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Davide Massimo,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 915

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. d(is) m(anibus) s(acrum)

2. Antonia Rufina

3. vix(it) ann(is) XLVIII

4. men(sibus) VI d(iebus) XV[---]

5. Ant[oni][---]

6. [---]

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

To the nether gods, Antonia Rufina, lived 48 years, 6 months, 15 days

Translation (it)

Agli dei Mani, Antonia Rufina, è vissuta per 48 anni, 6 mesi, 15 giorni

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285105

EDR 121178

EDCS 14800288

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 06.1207 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 56

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